

Менеджмент

УДК 378:005.7

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19322930>

**Парадигма демократичного та партнерського управління в закладах
вищої освіти**

Литвинов Олексій Миколайович

д.ю.н., професор

в.о. ректора Національний аерокосмічний університет

«Харківський авіаційний інститут»

м. Харків, вул. Вадима Манька, 17. Україна 61070

E-mail: lytvynovalex@gmail.com

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2952-8258>

Шевченко Ірина Олександрівна

д.е.н, доцент,

професор кафедри менеджменту та бізнес адміністрування

Національний аерокосмічний університет

«Харківський авіаційний інститут»

м. Харків, вул. Вадима Манька, 17. Україна 61070

Irina_shev4enko@ukr.net

ORCID: 0000-0001-8188-3551

Прийнято: 14.03.2026 | Опубліковано: 29.03.2026

Анотація: У статті досліджено парадигму демократичного та партнерського управління в закладах вищої освіти в умовах трансформації сучасного освітнього простору. Обґрунтовано, що еволюція університету від

класичної академічної інституції до багатомісійної організації зумовлює потребу в нових управлінських підходах, здатних забезпечити баланс між академічною автономією, внутрішньою колегіальністю та відкритістю до зовнішньої взаємодії. Метою статті є теоретичне обґрунтування парадигми демократичного та партнерського управління університетом нового типу. Використано загальнонаукові методи аналізу, синтезу, порівняння, узагальнення та концептуального моделювання. На основі аналізу наукової літератури та еволюції моделей університету визначено, що сучасний університет функціонує як складна інституційна система, яка поєднує риси академічної спільноти, організаційної структури та мережевої екосистеми. Встановлено, що демократичне управління ґрунтується на принципах академічної автономії, колегіальності, прозорості та участі академічної спільноти у прийнятті рішень, тоді як партнерське управління забезпечує інтеграцію університету в систему взаємодії з державою, бізнесом, науковими установами, громадами та міжнародними інституціями. Наукова новизна дослідження полягає в обґрунтуванні концепції університету нового типу як багатомісійної та інституційно складної організації, розвиток якої базується на демократичній участі, партнерській взаємодії та інтеграції в суспільство знань. Зроблено висновок, що демократичне та партнерське управління є ключовою умовою ефективного розвитку закладів вищої освіти в сучасних умовах.

Ключові слова: університет нового типу, менеджмент, академічна автономія, багатомісійність, третя місія університету.

The paradigm of democratic and partnership governance in higher education institutions

Lytvynov Oleksii

Doctor of Law, Professor

Acting Rector of the National Aerospace University “Kharkiv Aviation Institute”,

E-mail: lytvynovalex@gmail.com

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2952-8258>

Shevchenko Iryna

Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor,

Professor of the Department of Management and Business Administration

National Aerospace University “Kharkiv Aviation Institute”

e-mail: Irina_shev4enko@ukr.net

ORCID: 0000-0001-8188-3551

Abstract: The article explores the paradigm of democratic and partnership management in higher education institutions in the context of the transformation of the modern educational space. It is substantiated that the evolution of the university from a classical academic institution to a multi-mission organization necessitates the need for new management approaches capable of ensuring a balance between academic autonomy, internal collegiality and openness to external interaction. The aim of the article is to theoretically substantiate the paradigm of democratic and partnership management of a new type of university. General scientific methods of analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalization and conceptual modeling are used. Based on the analysis of scientific literature and the evolution of university models, it is determined that the modern university functions as a complex institutional system that combines the features of an academic community, organizational structure and network ecosystem. It was established that democratic governance is based on the principles of

academic autonomy, collegiality, transparency and participation of the academic community in decision-making, while partnership governance ensures the integration of the university into the system of interaction with the state, business, scientific institutions, communities and international institutions. The scientific novelty of the study lies in substantiating the concept of a new type of university as a multi-mission and institutionally complex organization, the development of which is based on democratic participation, partnership interaction and integration into the knowledge society. It is concluded that democratic and partnership governance is a key condition for the effective development of higher education institutions in modern conditions.

Keywords: university of a new type, management, academic autonomy, multi-mission nature, the third mission of the university.

Statement of the problem. Global problems of mankind have caused the transformation of all traditional processes of society's life. The higher education system, today, has not been left aside. Improvement, reformation and, finally, the global transformation of higher education institutions (hereinafter referred to as HEIs) has gone beyond the traditional idea of educational institutions. HEIs in modern conditions are acquiring the features of a complex multi-mission institution that combines educational, research and social functions. The expansion of the role of universities in the development of society, economy and culture necessitates the rethinking of their management models. European guidelines for the development of higher education play an important role, in particular the principles of academic freedom, institutional autonomy, transparency of management and partnership between universities and stakeholders. Universities are increasingly considered as open institutions that not only generate knowledge, but also actively interact with society, contributing to social, cultural and innovative development. In this context, democratic and partnership governance is not only a management technology, but also the institutional basis for the functioning of a new type of university. The relevance of the study is due to the need for a theoretical understanding of the transformation of

universities in the modern educational space and the justification of democratic and partnership governance models capable of ensuring the effective development of higher education institutions in conditions of institutional complexity, multi-mission and growing interaction with various social actors.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The issues of university transformation, their sustainability and role in socio-economic development are actively researched in modern scientific literature. Foreign studies have formed several conceptual approaches to the development of universities in a changing environment. In particular, B. Clark substantiates the model of an entrepreneurial university, which provides for organizational flexibility, resource diversification and increased managerial autonomy of higher education institutions (Clark, 1998). Further development of the idea of university interaction with the economy and society is reflected in the concept of the “triple helix” by G. Etzkowitz and L. Leydesdorff, which describes the interaction of the university, business and the state as the basis for innovative development (Etzkowitz, Leydesdorff, 2000). The issue of modernization of university management in the context of new approaches to public management is considered by H. de Boer, J. Enders and U. Schimank (2007). In the broader context of the development of universities as social institutions, R. Barnett proposes the concept of an “ecological university”, which actively interacts with various social systems and contributes to the sustainable development of society (Barnett, 2018). Also important is the study of the role of universities in regional development, which is presented in the works of R. Pinheiro, P. Benneworth and G. Jones (2012). In the Ukrainian scientific literature, the issues of university sustainability in crisis conditions, in particular during war, are studied in the works of O. M. Lytvynov and I. O. Shevchenko. The authors consider the concept of a sustainable university, the role of the third mission of the university in ensuring sustainable development, as well as innovative approaches to internal quality assurance of education in conditions of military challenges. Separate studies are devoted to the economic role of universities as knowledge centers in international networks of sustainability and the influence of

international economic relations on the institutional strategies of higher education institutions (Lytvynov, Shevchenko, 2025). Recent research highlights the growing integration of psychological and social approaches in understanding wellbeing and education. Bradshaw et al. (2026) apply Self-Determination Theory (SDT) to the analysis of social determinants of health, demonstrating that environmental conditions influence psychological wellbeing through the satisfaction or frustration of basic psychological needs—autonomy, competence, and relatedness. Their findings suggest that improved social conditions not only reduce psychological distress but also enhance overall wellbeing by supporting these fundamental needs.

In the educational context, Mucinskas et al. (2025) examine the role of communities of practice in shaping educators' expectations regarding student character development. The study shows that participation in such communities strengthens teachers' beliefs in students' capacity for moral and personal growth, while also contributing to professional development and pedagogical effectiveness.

Overall, these studies emphasize the importance of combining social and psychological perspectives. While SDT provides a robust framework for understanding the link between social conditions and individual wellbeing, communities of practice offer practical mechanisms for fostering holistic development within educational settings.

Thus, modern research emphasizes the need to transform universities into more flexible, innovative, and socially responsible institutions capable of ensuring the sustainable development of education, science, and society even in crisis conditions.

Highlighting previously unresolved parts of the overall problem. Despite the significant amount of scientific research devoted to the transformation of universities and the development of modern management models in the field of higher education, a number of important aspects of this issue remain insufficiently researched. In particular, the scientific literature widely considers the issues of the entrepreneurial university, the innovative role of universities in the development of the knowledge economy, as well as the interaction of the university, the state and business within the

framework of the concept of the "triple helix". At the same time, the institutional logic of combining democratic principles of university management with partnership forms of interaction with the external environment has been revealed to a much lesser extent.

The issues of harmonizing internal mechanisms of academic self-government with new models of strategic and network management of universities that operate in complex socio-economic and innovation ecosystems remain insufficiently researched. Also, modern research presents a limited conceptual understanding of the university as a multi-mission institutional system that simultaneously combines the functions of the academic community, organizational structure and open network platform for interaction with various stakeholders.

A separate scientific problem is the theoretical substantiation of the model of a new type of university, in which democratic mechanisms of internal management are combined with partnership forms of interaction with the state, business, scientific institutions, civil society and international institutions. It is this integration of internal and external management mechanisms that creates the prerequisites for the formation of a new management paradigm for the development of universities in the modern knowledge society.

Thus, the issue of forming a holistic paradigm of democratic and partnership management of a new type of university, which allows combining academic autonomy, collegiality of decision-making and strategic interaction of the university with a wide range of social actors, requires further theoretical understanding.

The purpose of the study is to theoretically substantiate the paradigm of democratic and partnership-based university management of a new type in the context of the transformation of the modern higher education system.

Results. The evolution of the university as a social institution reflects profound changes in the methods of knowledge production, education organization, and science-society interaction. During historical development, the university gradually transformed from a relatively closed academic community to a complex multi-mission organization integrated into social, economic, and innovation ecosystems. These

transformations were accompanied not only by the expansion of the university's functions, but also by a significant change in the management logic of its functioning.

In the classical university model, which was formed in the European tradition of the Middle Ages, the university was considered primarily as a community of scientists and students united by the practice of teaching and intellectual search. The main function of the university was the transfer of knowledge, and management was based on the principles of academic autonomy and collegial self-government. Management decisions were formed within the academic community. Such a system was effective in conditions of relative stability and a limited scale of university activity.

The further development of universities is associated with the formation of a research model of the university. In this model, an institutional combination of education and scientific research took place, which significantly changed the role of the university in society. The university ceases to be only an institution for the transfer of knowledge and becomes a space for its systematic production. The change in the functional purpose of the university also led to the transformation of management mechanisms: along with collegial forms, the role of academic leadership, scientific schools and research structures is growing.

In the second half of the 20th century, a mass model of the university is being formed, which is associated with the expansion of access to higher education and the growth in the number of students. The massification of higher education has led to a significant complication of the organizational structure of universities, the emergence of a large number of educational programs, administrative units and management procedures. In these conditions, collegial management mechanisms are gradually supplemented by elements of administrative planning, bureaucratization of management processes and professionalization of the management apparatus.

At the end of the 20th - beginning of the 21st century, in the conditions of the development of the knowledge economy, an entrepreneurial model of the university is being formed. The university begins to actively interact with the economic environment, participate in the creation of innovations, technology transfer and the

development of regional innovation systems. In this model, the role of strategic management, diversification of funding sources, development of partnerships with business and state structures is significantly increasing. The management logic of the university is gradually shifting from administrative management to strategic management focused on development, competitiveness and innovative activity.

Further complication of the university operating environment, the development of digital technologies, globalization of science and education, as well as the growth of the role of network forms of cooperation lead to the formation of an ecosystem model of the university. Instead of an isolated institution, the university becomes an open platform for the co-creation of knowledge and innovation.

Thus, the historical evolution of the university demonstrates the gradual complication of its mission structure. If early universities functioned mainly within the framework of an educational mission, then modern universities simultaneously implement an educational, research and social mission. This leads to the formation of a multi-mission architecture of the university, which significantly complicates its organizational structure and management mechanisms.

The growth of the university's multi-mission is accompanied by the emergence of new forms of management aimed at coordinating different areas of activity, balancing the interests of various stakeholders and ensuring the strategic development of the university. Under these conditions, the university is gradually transforming into a complex institutional system that combines the features of an academic community, an organization and a network ecosystem.

Analysis of the evolution of university models allows us to trace the natural transformation of its functional purpose, organizational structure and management logic. The models presented in the table demonstrate that the development of the university does not occur by completely replacing one model with another. On the contrary, historical university models are gradually layered, preserving individual elements and forming a complex multi-level institutional structure of the modern university.

Table 1

Evolution of university models and transformation of managerial logic

University model	Historical period	Dominant mission	Organizational characteristics	Management logic	Type of interaction with the environment
Classic	Middle Ages – Early Modern	Educational	Academic corporation of teachers and students	Collegial self-government	Limited interaction
Research	19th century	Educational + research	Academic institution of scientific research	Academic leadership	Scientific networks
Mass	mid-20th century	Education (mass)	Multidisciplinary educational organization	Administrative planning	State education system
Entrepreneurial	end of the 20th century.	Three missions	Innovative organization	Strategic management	Business, industry
Ecosystem	21st century.	Integrated missions	Network institution	Partnership management	Innovative ecosystems

The classical university model was focused mainly on the educational mission and functioned as an autonomous academic corporation, the management of which was based on the principles of collegial self-government. The formation of the research model of the university expanded the functional framework of the university by integrating scientific research, which contributed to the strengthening of the role of academic leadership and the development of scientific schools. The massification of higher education in the middle of the twentieth century led to a further complication of the organizational structure of universities and the emergence of administrative mechanisms for planning and management.

The emergence of the entrepreneurial model of the university at the end of the 20th century was a response to the challenges of the knowledge economy and strengthened the orientation of universities towards innovative activity, strategic management and partnership with the economic environment. In turn, the modern ecosystem model of the university reflects a further stage of development, within which

the university functions as an open network institution integrated into complex social and innovation ecosystems.

Thus, the evolution of university models is accompanied by a gradual expansion of its missions and an increase in organizational complexity. The university is moving from a relatively holistic educational institution to a multi-mission organization combining educational, research and social functions.

Thus, the modern university can be considered as the result of the historical layering of various development models, which forms the prerequisites for the emergence of a new type of university. The development of which is based on the principles of democratic participation, partnership and integration into wider social and innovation ecosystems.

The scientific novelty lies in the justification of the transition from traditional university models to the concept of a new-type university as a multi-mission and institutionally complex organization. The new-type university is considered as the result of the historical layering of different development models, which necessitates the need for new management approaches based on a combination of democratic and partnership management.

A modern university should be considered not only as an organization that provides educational services, but as a special type of social institution that combines an intellectual community, scientific infrastructure and a complex management system. Historically, the university emerged as an academic corporation of teachers and students united by a common practice of teaching, discussion and interpretation of knowledge. That is why in the classical European tradition the university was considered primarily as a community of thought that functions on the basis of the principles of academic freedom, collegiality and autonomy.

In the process of historical development, the university gradually acquires the features of a complex organization. The expansion of the scope of activities, the diversification of educational programs, the development of scientific research, international cooperation and the growth of interaction with the external environment

lead to the formation of a branched administrative structure and the emergence of professional management. The university begins to function as an organizational system that includes various structural units, management procedures, planning mechanisms and performance assessment.

Fig. 1. Evolution of university models and formation of a new type of university

Source: author's development

Thus, the institutional nature of the modern university is manifested in the combination of two interrelated dimensions: the academic community and the organizational management system. The academic community is formed around disciplinary traditions, scientific interests, professional ethics and practices of collective search for knowledge. Its unity is supported not by the administrative hierarchy, but by intellectual authority, scientific reputation and participation in joint academic procedures. It is within this community that such fundamental principles of university activity as academic freedom, research autonomy and collegial discussion of scientific and educational issues function.

Along with this, the university functions as a complex organization, the activities of which require effective resource management, coordination of various areas of activity and interaction with numerous external actors. Modern universities have a multi-level management structure, which includes the rectorate, faculties, institutes, research centers, administrative units and other organizational elements. In the context of expanding the functions of the university and the growth of its role in society, the organizational component of the university is becoming increasingly important.

An important characteristic of the modern university is its multi-mission. Unlike early university models, which were focused mainly on the educational function, the modern university implements at least three main missions: educational, research and social. The educational mission is related to the training of specialists and the formation of the intellectual potential of society. The research mission is aimed at the production of new knowledge, the development of science and innovation. The third mission involves the interaction of the university with society, the economy and the regional environment, in particular through knowledge transfer, innovative activities and social initiatives.

The implementation of these missions forms a multidimensional structure of university activities and leads to an increase in the organizational complexity of the university. Each of the missions has its own logic of functioning, different time horizons, performance criteria and a range of stakeholders. Educational activities are

focused on the stability of curricula and standards of specialist training, scientific activities are associated with the uncertainty of the research process, and the social mission involves a rapid response to the needs of socio-economic development. The coordination of these different logics of activity creates additional managerial complexity.

In this regard, the modern university is increasingly viewed as a complex institutional system that combines different types of rationality and organizational mechanisms. On the one hand, the university retains the features of an academic community that supports intellectual traditions and ensures the development of knowledge. On the other hand, it functions as an organization that requires strategic management, effective use of resources and active interaction with various social institutions.

Thus, the institutional nature of the modern university is manifested in its ability to combine academic values with organizational management mechanisms. It is this duality that determines the specifics of the development of universities in modern society and forms the basis for the emergence of new models of university management based on the principles of democratic participation and partnership.

Therefore, the interpretation of a modern university as a living institution that combines the academic community and the organizational management system is a methodologically new postulate. This approach allows us to consider the university not only as a formal educational organization, but as a complex institutional system that combines the intellectual autonomy of the academic community and the need for effective organizational management.

In the current conditions of the transition to a knowledge society, the role of universities is significantly transformed. If the traditional university mainly performed the functions of transferring knowledge and training specialists, today it is becoming a key element in the development of an innovative economy, scientific research and social progress. Universities are not only educational institutions, but also centers for the generation of new ideas, technologies and social changes.

Fig. 2. The institutional nature of a modern university as a combination of an academic community and an organizational management system

The knowledge society is characterized by rapid information updating, globalization of the educational space and active interaction between science, business and the state. In these conditions, universities must adapt to new challenges: ensure interdisciplinarity of education, stimulate scientific research, support innovative activities and develop partnerships with various public institutions. That is why there

is a need to form a new type of university, capable of functioning effectively in the dynamic environment of the modern world.

One of the key prerequisites for the formation of such a university is the need for new management models. Traditional administrative and hierarchical approaches are gradually being replaced by more flexible management systems based on the principles of autonomy, academic freedom, openness and strategic management. A new type of university is oriented towards decentralization of management, involvement of various stakeholders in decision-making, as well as effective use of resources to achieve educational and scientific goals.

An important aspect of the activities of a new type of university is its multi-mission. In addition to the traditional functions of education and science, modern universities actively carry out social, cultural and innovative missions. They contribute to the development of civil society, form critical thinking in students, support entrepreneurial initiative and participate in solving urgent social problems.

Thus, a new type of university can be defined as an open institution that operates on the basis of the principles of democracy, partnership and multi-mission. Such a university integrates educational, scientific and social activities, actively interacts with the state, business and civil society and acts as an important factor in the development of a knowledge society.

Therefore, the proposed conceptual definition of a new type of university as an open institution that operates on the basis of democracy, partnership and multi-mission, ensuring the integration of educational, scientific and social activities in the conditions of the formation of a knowledge society, is new in formal and substantive terms.

One of the key characteristics of democratic university governance is academic autonomy, which provides for the right of a higher education institution to independently determine educational policy, areas of scientific research, management structure and mechanisms of internal organization of activities. Academic autonomy creates conditions for flexible response to the challenges of the modern educational environment and contributes to improving the quality of education and science.

An important component of democratic governance is collegiality, which is manifested in the involvement of representatives of various groups of the academic community in the process of strategic decision-making. Collegiate governance bodies, such as academic councils, faculty councils and student self-government bodies, ensure a balance of interests and contribute to the formation of joint responsibility for the development of the university.

For a more systematic understanding of the features of the democratic model of university governance, it is advisable to consider its main characteristics and management mechanisms (Table 2).

Table 2

The main elements of a democratic model of university governance

Element of democratic governance	Content	Management role
Academic autonomy	The right of the university to independently determine educational, scientific and personnel policies	Provides management flexibility and adaptation to changes in the field of education
Collegiality	Making important decisions through collegial bodies (academic council, faculty councils)	Ensures a balance of interests of different groups in the academic community
Academic community participation	Involving teachers, researchers and students in management processes	Increases the legitimacy of decisions and the level of responsibility
Management transparency	Openness of decision-making procedures and access to information	Promotes trust within the university community
Partnership between administration and academia	Cooperation of management structures with scientific and pedagogical staff	Aligns the strategic and academic interests of the university

As can be seen from Table 2, the democratic model of university governance is based on a combination of autonomy, collegiality and active participation of the academic community in decision-making. Such principles create conditions for the formation of an effective management system that takes into account the interests of different groups of the university community and promotes the development of the institution. The scientific novelty lies in the disclosure of democratic university

governance as a mechanism for harmonizing the academic and administrative logics of the functioning of a university institution in the context of modern transformations of the higher education system.

A feature of a modern university is its functioning in a network of partnerships, where educational, scientific and innovative activities are carried out in interaction with various social and economic actors. In such a system, the university acts not only as a generator of knowledge, but also as an intermediary between science, business and society, contributing to the transfer of technologies, the development of entrepreneurship and the formation of an innovative environment.

To systematize the main areas of partnership interaction of the university, it is advisable to consider key groups of partners and their role in the development of the university (Table 3).

Table 3

Main areas of partnership cooperation of the university

Partner group	Forms of cooperation	Significance for the development of the university
Business and employers	Joint educational programs, student internships, participation in the formation of curricula	Increasing the practical focus of education and the competitiveness of graduates
State authorities	Educational and scientific projects, participation in the development of educational policy	Alignment of university activities with state development priorities
Research institutions	Joint research, scientific consortia, academic mobility	Development of scientific potential and interdisciplinary research
International universities and organizations	Academic exchange programs, international research projects	Integration into the global educational and scientific space
Local communities and public organizations	Social projects, educational initiatives, cultural events	Strengthening the social role of the university in regional development

As can be seen from Table 3, the partnership management model provides for multi-vector interaction of the university with various subjects of social life. Such cooperation contributes to the formation of a network structure of the university's activities, where educational and scientific processes are combined with the practical

needs of the economy and society. The university acts as a center for intellectual and civic development, promotes the formation of democratic values, supports cultural initiatives and participates in the development of regional communities. The implementation of this mission is largely based on the university's partnership with government bodies, public organizations, local communities and international institutions. Thus, democratic and partnership principles of management create institutional conditions for a harmonious combination of the university's educational, research and social missions. They ensure the coordination of interests of various participants in the university environment, promote the university's openness to external interactions and increase the effectiveness of its activities in the conditions of modern social changes.

Fig. 3. Democratic and partnership management model as an institutional basis for balancing university missions

Source: author's development

Fig. 3 summarizes the results of the study and reflects the conceptual model of the relationship between democratic and partnership governance and the main missions of a modern university. The presented scheme demonstrates that the effective implementation of the educational, research and social missions of the university is possible only if an appropriate institutional management environment is formed, which combines the principles of academic democracy and systemic interaction with stakeholders.

Conclusions. Thus, the conducted research allows us to conclude that democratic and partnership management is the key institutional basis for the functioning of a new type of university. It ensures the balancing of various missions of the university, contributes to increasing the efficiency of its activities and creates conditions for the integration of the university into the modern knowledge society. The combination of democratic mechanisms of internal management and partnership forms of interaction with the external environment forms a new management paradigm for the development of universities, which meets the modern challenges of globalization, innovative development and the growth of the role of universities in society.

References

1. Lytvynov O. M. Zabezpechennia stiikosti pryfrontovoho universytetu: 15 ese pro dosvid KhAI [Ensuring the sustainability of a frontline university: 15 essays on the experience of KhAI]. Kyiv: Pravo, 2025.
2. Lytvynov O. M., Shevchenko I. O. Tretia misiia universytetu yak mekhanizm stiikoho rozvytku: nova paradyhma vyshchoi osvity Ukrainy // Chasopys ekonomichnykh reform. 2025. № 4 (60). S. 85–99.
3. Lytvynov O. M., Shevchenko I. O. Model universytetu stiikoho typu: innovatsiini pidkhody do vnutrishnoho zabezpechennia yakosti osvity v umovakh viiny // Propilei prava ta bezpeky. 2025. № 8. S. 22–33. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.32620/pls.2025.8.02>

4. Barnett R. The ecological university: a feasible utopia. London: Routledge, 2018.
5. Clark B. R. Creating entrepreneurial universities: organizational pathways of transformation. Oxford: Pergamon Press, 1998.
6. De Boer H., Enders J., Schimank U. On the way towards new public management? The governance of university systems in England, the Netherlands, Austria, and Germany // New forms of governance in research organizations / ed. by D. Jansen. Dordrecht: Springer, 2007. P. xx–xx.
7. Etzkowitz H., Leydesdorff L. The triple helix: university–industry–government innovation in action. New York: Routledge, 2000.
8. Lytvynov O., Shevchenko I. O. Knowledge hubs in times of crisis: the economic and strategic role of universities in international resilience networks // Actual Problems of International Relations. 2025. Vol. 165, № 1. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17721/apmv.2025.165.1.123-136>
9. Lytvynov O., Shevchenko I. O. Managing sustainability in higher education: the impact of international economic relations on institutional strategies // Actual Problems of International Relations. 2025. Vol. 164, № 1. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17721/apmv.2025.164.1.106-116>
10. Pinheiro R., Benneworth P., Jones G. A. Universities and regional development: a critical assessment of tensions and contradictions. London: Routledge, 2012.
11. Emma L. Bradshaw, Cody R. DeHaan, Adam Neufeld, Sandra Diaz-Castillo & Richard M. Ryan (25 Feb 2026): A self-determination theory approach to the social determinants of health and psychological wellbeing, Psychology, Health & Medicine, DOI: 10.1080/13548506.2026.2636307
12. Mucinskas D, Clark S, Barendsen L and Gardner H (2025) An increase in educator expectations of student character growth during participation in a community of practice. Front. Educ. 10:1466295. doi: 10.3389/feduc.2025.1466295